

COMPUTATIONAL MECHANICAL METAMATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this work is to introduce both passive and active approaches for achieving advanced computational properties for enabling new metamaterial applications. More specifically, these approaches achieve computational capabilities via (i) passive architectures that consist of simple micro-sized beam elements organized within multi-stable switching mechanisms that mimic mechanical logic-gates, or (ii) active architectures that consist of embedded actuators and sensors that utilize external power and control to train the architecture's properties as a mechanical neural network. Applications include power-free compact materials that can perform calculations in extreme environments that would damage conventional electronic chips or aircraft wings that can learn to exhibit optimal air foil shapes as they are exposed to differing flight conditions in real-time.

1 INTRODUCTION

Mechanical metamaterials (a.k.a., architected materials) achieve desired system-level properties primarily from their microarchitecture instead of their composition. By engineering the type, locations, and orientations of flexible elements (e.g., beams) that constitute the microarchitecture of such materials, advanced computational capabilities can be achieved. Such capabilities include the ability to perform simple calculations in response to external stimuli or to learn desired properties through continued exposure to changes in ambient conditions. These computational properties can be achieved via (i) passive architectures that consist of simple micro-sized beam elements organized within multi-stable switching mechanisms that mimic mechanical logic-gates, or (ii) active architectures that consist of embedded actuators and sensors that utilize external power and control to train the architecture's properties as a mechanical neural network. The aim of this work is to introduce such passive and active approaches for achieving advanced computational properties for enabling new metamaterial applications (e.g., power-free compact materials that can perform calculations in extreme environments that would damage conventional electronic chips or aircraft wings that can learn to exhibit optimal air foil shapes as they are exposed to differing flight conditions in real-time).

2 APPROACHES FOR ACHIEVING COMPUTATIONAL BEHAVIOR

2.1 Passive Computational Metamaterials

Metamaterials can be designed to passively perform calculations by creating a functionally complete library of flexure-based multi-stable logic gates. An example of a bi-stable constituent unit that could enable such a library is provided in Fig. 1. This fundamental unit must be fabricated with straight and undeformed flexures as shown in Fig. 1a but must then be preloaded a distance h (Fig. 1b) beyond a critical buckling point at which the unit's stage, labelled s in the figure, is stable a distance d_s above or below its original position. It's important that the unit be designed with a symmetric energy profile (Fig. 1c) so that the same state of energy is stored in the unit in either stable configuration. This symmetric energy profile enables many such units joined together to trigger a cascade of state switching with minimal energy losses if one of the units in the chain is actuated to a different state.

Thus, using the fundamental unit of Fig. 1 a functionally complete library of mechanical logic gates (e.g., AND, OR, NOT, NOR, and NAND gates) can be designed, which can be joined together within a new kind of metamaterial to passively perform simple calculations [1]. A fabricated NOR gate

example is shown in Fig. 2 for every combination of its two inputs “A” and “B”. Although others have explored various approaches for achieving mechanical logic [2], the proposed approach is the first that is simultaneously (i) functionally complete, (ii) continuous, (iii) scalable, and (iv) stores constant energy across different logic states. The idea is also extendable to 3D designs that pack many logic gates into small volumes.

Figure 1: (a) Fundamental unit prior to deformation; (b) deformed unit shown in its two stable states; (c) energy versus stage displacement plot.

Figure 2: Example NOR gate showing its four possible input (A and B) and output combinations.

2.2 Active Computational Metamaterials

Metamaterials can be designed to actively learn their properties by drawing from the inspiration of artificial neural networks [3]. If the neurons within such networks are replaced by mechanical nodes and the weights depicted as lines are replaced by beams with tunable axial stiffness values (Fig. 3), a new metamaterial emerges that utilizes a mechanical neural network to learn its properties. The axial stiffness of such beams can be actively tuned via control using actuators and sensors to achieve a material that can exhibit desired properties. Such properties include the ability to learn desired shape changes in response to external loading conditions as well as the ability to perform calculations on incident acoustic waves by transforming their amplitude, wavelength, and frequency as desired.

Figure 3: Mechanical neural network metamaterials are analogous to artificial neural networks.

3 CONCLUSIONS

This paper introduces passive and active approaches for achieving materials that perform computational capabilities that include the ability to perform simple calculations and/or learn their behaviours via repeated exposure. These approaches include multi-stable buckled flexure elements that behave as logic gates and actively controlled beams within a latticed network that constitutes a mechanical neural network.

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